
Political aspect of ethnopsychological and socio-cultural features of a country's population

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Abstract

An attempt to synthesize theoretical developments in industry of political communication is done in the article, the stages of research of this phenomenon are selected in political science and the features of political communication are determined in the conditions of modern society. Socio-cultural features of the population of different states, influence on politics, social development of society are analyzed.

Key words: communication, political communication, concept of political communication, theory of political communication, socio-cultural features, social development of society.

Introduction

The human society has always strived to gain a comprehensive knowledge of ethnic features of nationalities, their socio-cultural patterns of conduct. These traits were studied by psychologists, philosophers, historians, social scientists, political scientists, geographers, economists, fine art experts, ethnographers, culturologists, theologians, and demographers. The studies of ethnic features of nationalities, their character and psychology continue to be relevant today, as different aspects of this issue have become cornerstones in the dynamic processes of social development.

Deep understanding of the ethnopsychological personal characteristics, adequate evaluation of the phenomena of interethnic differences of the psyche, their influence on the processes of interaction between different ethnic groups are necessary to address a set of problems faced by the praxis of political life, education and upbringing, psychological support of individual

development. It is possible to ensure the formation of national identity, to form cultural ethnic, language and cross-cultural competences based on the cultural heritage of a nationality, ability to identify and use the national-psychological features.

Political, economic, cultural, scientific relations between the states are propelling the issue of interethnic communication. Such communication should take due account of the ethnopsychological characteristics of the subjects of interaction and make optimal use of their influence in all spheres of activity.

Specific national forms of information transmission required for the spatial stability and cultural integration of an ethnic group contribute to the consolidation of ethnic culture, individualize an ethnic group, and ensure internal integrity, distinctiveness and uniqueness of this ethnic culture (Political Science Encyclopedic Dictionary, 2017).

Analysis of recent research and publications

Ethnopsychology as a branch of psychological science and, at the same time, of political science, which studies the psychological features of nations and cultures, is of particular interest to the

researchers (Platonov, 2019). Many academic papers have noted that bridging the language gap is only possible through studying and mastering the ethnopsychological features of a nationality

(Piren, 1998).

The goal of this research is to analyze the ethnopsychological and sociocultural aspects of a nation and their role in the formation of national character, national idea, and in highlighting the traits of a nation's mindset.

Proceeding from the set goal, it is necessary to address the tasks as follows:

- to study socio-cultural phenomena;
- to analyze the typical qualities and psychological traits of a county's population;
- to highlight main features of communication;
- to reveal the peculiarities of manifestation of the national character;
- based on the factual evidence, to confirm the need to factor into ethnopsychological characteristics of a nationality in various spheres of political life, as well as to elaborate a system of a foreign language command, proficiency and skills.

The analysis of recent research articles and publications shows that ethnopsychological research efforts are quite relevant today. A special program of standard ethnopsychological research has been developed. This program contains a set of standardized methods that have been adapted and modernized to study the ethnopsychological traits of representatives of an ethnic community [4]. The professional methods are also employed to study the ethnic stereotypes, behavioral patterns and direct reactions of people to members of other ethnic groups, i.e. a natural experiment is conducted (Piren, 1998).

Having analyzed the ethnic character and self-

consciousness of an ethnic group, most researchers distinguish individual and group levels of ethnic identity. It is characterized as an integral system of self-perceptions of an individual, which is closely related to the formed image of own ethnic group. These researchers are: T. Voropaieva, G. Grabovich, V. Krysko, O. Nelga, D. Olshansky, V. Pavlenko, V. Pauchok, A. Ponomarev, V. Yaniv and others (Political Science Encyclopedic Dictionary, 2017).

Ethnopsychology as a scientific discipline dates back as far as the 60s of the XIX century. It was understood as a system of cognition of the psychological state of a nation through a comparative analysis of the language, morals, mythology and culture of individuals sharing common features of the psyche. Paper of W. Wundt "Psychology of Nations" (1930s-1950s) gave an impetus to the development of ethnopsychology (Komarovskiy, 2011).

The concept of "Spirit of a Nation" was akin to the neo-Freudian theory of "Culture and Personality", which derived the national character from a set of "modal" persons, considering ethnicity to be a socio-biological phenomenon. This concept became the basis for ethnopsychological research efforts of Ukrainian scientists O. Kulchytsky and V. Yaniv. O. Kulchytsky identified the somatopsychic, *geopsychic*, historical, social, cultural-morphic, and the innermost unconscious aspects of the formation of the Ukrainian psyche (Popova, 2019). V. Yaniv, above all, highlighted the historical and socio-psychological factors of formation of the Ukrainian psychotype (Grachev, 2014).

Results and discussion

Learning foreign languages is gaining in importance in modern society as well. It is essential to employ a range of techniques and methods for the development of philological, translation, cross-cultural skills, and language proficiency.

Modern linguistic theory and practice places emphasis on the formation of professional communicative competence through the development and improvement of all types of speech activity: reading, speaking, writing, and

listening. The efficiency of the process of a foreign language teaching is directly dependent on the consideration of various ethnopsychological aspects.

The core concept of the socio-biological nature of ethnicity formed the basis of national ethnography and ethnopsychology, the priorities of which were ethnic identity and national character as a basis for understanding the "purpose" of the Ukrainian nation.

A significant contribution to consideration of

the formation of the Ukrainian national identity was made by the historian J. Dashkevych, who developed a concept of ethnogenesis of Ukrainians as an independent nation with several levels of identity. According to J. Dashkevych, the basis of the ethnic system is the national idea, which excites national identity and becomes a driver for the formation of national culture (Dashkevych J., Moskovichi S., 2019).

At the same time, it should be noted that the theory and practice of identifying, diagnosing and understanding the ethnopsychological features of nations and nationalities have not been fully formed yet. Relevant issues are actively worked out by experts of different knowledge areas (psychology, sociology, ethnology, political science, pedagogy) to create an effective methodology and rationale for the study of national psychological phenomena (Kosenko, 2011). However, in our opinion, very few papers discuss the role of ethnopsychological and sociocultural drivers in the political processes.

Intensive efforts in this direction enable to understand the role of different methods in the holistic process of research, help to overcome the existing theoretical discrepancies.

Understanding of ethnopsychological issues, methods and research activities makes it possible to obtain the most accurate results in the study of such a complex phenomenon as national identity, and contribute to the successful settlement of political issues related to national interests (McQueel, 2010).

The national character, culture, traditions, sustainable models of education, communication, and rank of a particular state in the world community are mirroring the individuality of ethnopsychological features of a nationality.

Ethnic and national problems are topping the list of problems twisted into the complex palette of socio-political relations. Such concepts as “nationality”, “nation”, “ethnic group” are often interpreted synonymously, but they have significant differences. Yes, “nationality” and “nation” are identical concepts that determine the biological origin of a group of people, but in socio-political terms they are different.

Nationality is a biological unity, a group of people united by blood, biological ties (Kosenko,

2011). Speaking of any nationality, it can be argued that it was formed as a result mixing with other nationalities and is a consequence of historical development.

However, the essence of a nationality is not limited to the biological origin, because it is living in a certain space. Space as a place of permanent settlement of a nationality is a critical factor in its existence, which is supplemented with another critical component – the language. People use the language to communicate; language launches the beginning of spiritual life of a nationality.

An ethnic group is a stable group of people who belong to a certain nationality, live in the territory or as part of another nationality, preserving their culture, way of life, language and psychological features. The character of an ethnic group is not a sum of characters of its individual members. This is primarily an imprint of typical features that are inherent to a different extent to most individuals of this ethnic group.

A person perceives himself indirectly, with the help of other people, members of his ethnic group, by interpreting their reactions to his behavior and personality. Personal identity is a person's awareness of himself as an individual. This is a necessary condition and a managerial component of any conscious human activity: political, cultural, social (Schwartzenberg, 2018).

Ethnic identity at the level of an ethnic group acts as a system of general ideas of the majority of members of the ethnic group about their own ethnic group, its origin, the main features of culture and mental composition, i.e. as a system of collective self-perception.

A nation, in turn, is formed on the basis of several ethnic groups living in a certain area and connected by a certain type of socio-economic relations.

That is why, in the implementation of foreign policy, analysis of the political environment and forecasting the development of political processes, it is impossible to ignore the ethnopsychological features of the population, various ethno-linguistic elements that saturate the national language and manifest themselves in many forms: differences between the colloquial and literary norm, spoken and written speech.

Understanding the typical qualities and

psychological characteristics of an ethnic group enables to better define the concept of national character.

Culture of an ethnic community is not a simple sum of cultures of its members. It absorbs a set of pieces of work, values and behavioral patterns that are recognized by the ethnic community and have acquired important social, ethical and moral significance for its members. Not every component of the individual culture of community

members becomes the common asset of the whole ethnic community.

A distinction is made between culture of an ethnic community and cultural heritage passed down from generation to generation. Culture of an ethnic community is a set of real, relevant, operable pieces of works and patterns that play a recognized role in the lives of all members of the ethnic community.

Conclusions

Proceeding from the above, we can conclude:

1. Ethnopsychological features of both a particular individual and a nation are a logical interaction between culture and traditions of a particular nationality.

2. Absorption of mentality of an ethnic group provides the basis for understanding the national character, better insight into political life of a country, various cross-cultural phenomena.

3. Ethnic mentality is manifested in the specifics of world perception, dominant personal attitude to life, household and holidays arrangement, system of moral requirements and norms, forms of relations between people, etc.

4. Understanding of ethnopsychological features of the population creates a basis for elaboration of a system of French language command, proficiency and skills, ability to freely apply the acquired knowledge during oral and written communication, mastering the basics of

regional studies.

5. Absorption of mentality of an ethnic group contributes to the understanding of communication challenges, establishment of interlingual and intercultural contacts.

6. Ethnopsychological features are mirroring the worldview of the nationality, its political and cultural life.

Prospects for further research. Political communication and ethnopsychology have much in common with the general process of communication, but there are features: it permeates all levels of communication – from the inside personal and global; each political system creates its own network of political communication in accordance with its ethnopsychological features. Communication between the level of economic development of society, psychology and the level of development of political communication structures needs to be studied.

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